
The social impact of Internet based content for young people

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Abstract

Research background: Globalization and digitalization are currently two imperatives for socio-economic development at the local, regional and national level. The leading role of these processes in shaping socio-economic realities in the short and long term also seems indisputable. It is not only legal conditions that cannot keep up with the dynamics of technological change equally problematic is the sphere of behavioral relations of science education which is increasingly affected by digitization. The study reveals that the digital divide has evolved and should currently be studied based on more complex set of factors not just based on the accessibility to the global resources. As are different perspectives in defining digital divide also culturally and socially this divide should be considered.

Purpose of the article The purpose of the study was to examine also in the field of access to the global network by users of culturally different territories such as South East Asia, Western Balkans, Eastern Europe and also to study in relation to behavioral elements including the dangers of excessive use of the Internet.

Methods: In order to achieve the paper goals the critical literature analysis have been performed as well as the web based questionnaire survey made. The empirical material have been processed with SPSS software methods.

Findings & value added: The specific divide is of generational dimension thus younger ones are of special attention and their behaviors are interesting based on different culturally and territorially viewpoints. As digital accessibility is of high importance and still growing the problematic Internet usage should also be addressed thus studying what contents could be defined as harmful and affecting young generation of users. This work contributes to this topic and also incorporates research results on current state of accessibility in different culturally regions of the world.

Keywords: digital divide, digitalization, internet addiction

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1. Introduction

There is an ongoing increase in users with access to the Internet, and increasingly this access is also being provided via smartphones (Wang et al., 2024a; Wang et al., 2024b, Çoban, 2019). Mobility is fostering an extended ability to access the resources of the global network at virtually any place and at any time. The very issue of interest in the impact of browsing online resources on usage is present in the literature (Wessel et al., 2019), particularly in the context of negative consequences on human health. A negative expression of accessing content and browsing online resources is addiction, the importance of which has been recognized in the behaviour of young people. Both mobility and the participation of young people in the development of technological progress are important topics. In studies of students' behaviour in the context of their use of Internet-enabled devices, it is impossible not to notice the benefits, which include (Mazya et al., 2023) the availability and ease of access to information, the speed of access to data, the ease of obtaining data, and, consequently, the facilitation of the creation of scientific papers and the implementation of research. As the research results show, technology fosters the search for information for solutions of a creative nature.

Spending more time on online resources to prepare papers or study has a positive impact on academic performance also not insignificant is the fact of the communication and socialisation opportunities provided by the global network. The positive impact that Internet access gives users is due to what kind of online sources and resources they browse (Michikyan et al., 2015). With regard to the so-called "positive resources," which include educational resources and to which access is increasingly facilitated (Wu et al., 2010), resulting in the practical disappearance of geographic barriers to the process of acquiring knowledge, it is possible to speak here of excessive devotion of time to their use, which thus affects the hallmarks of addiction. This type of addiction can be characterised as positive given that, as a result, learners achieve better learning results.

In contrast to the positive role provided by access to and use of sources for academic purposes, access to non-educational types of resources can bring adverse effects, which are defined in the literature as resulting from Addictive Internet Usage (AIU) (Adorjan et al., 2021), among others, and whose effects have been studied particularly among younger people, including students. The indicated negative impacts of the Internet were identified and categorised according to the following key (Adorjan et al., 2021): social networking, random browsing, information searches and pornography. The very assertion of addiction stems from the fact of a person's decreasing level of control over his or her own rational behaviour (Çoban, 2019), particularly in the area of usage. Although observations and conclusions in this area, the reliability of which is not in doubt, have been presented extensively, Internet addiction has not yet been classified within the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Diseases (OSM-5), specifically, addiction to smartphone use.

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Other identified areas of addictive use of Internet resources include gambling, online shopping, communication, entertainment (Adorjan et al., 2021; Maqableh et al., 2021). Depression is associated with addictive use of Internet resources, as well as social exclusion (Wang et al., 2024a; Wang et al., 2024b), and this threat, too, according to researchers, should be recognized as a health and psychological problem in groups of young people. Among the categorised negative because addictive factors that characterise the use of Internet resources is Internet gaming addiction (IGA) (Hammad & Al-Shahrani, 2024).

In addition to the term AIU, the literature also includes "problematic internet behaviours (Pisani et al., 2017; Sánchez-Fernández & Borda-Mas, 2023), or cyber addictions (Chen & Jiang, 2020), among others. Studies isolate the growing danger from smartphone use (Grant et al., 2019). The negative effects observed in young people is the excessive use of social media. The result of this addiction is a state of threat to the sense of psychological stability, as well as the threat of feeling socially excluded. For this reason, in addition to the term "problematic internet use" (PIU), the term problematic smartphone use (PSU) is also mentioned. In addition to the identified dangers of psychological and social exclusion, there are also factors such as the achievement of poorer academic performance (Grant et al., 2019), or problems with sleepiness and sleep deprivation (Yang et al., 2020), but also problems with alcohol abuse (Grant et al., 2019). The problematic nature of the aforementioned addictions and their associated risks relate to the increasing levels of aggression and impulsiveness diagnosed in people with this condition. As studies have shown, there are correlations between addiction and levels of aggression and impulsiveness.

These dangers need to be recognized and responded to appropriately, primarily of a medical nature given the target group affected. The issue of young people's behavior in terms of accessibility to Internet resources is an important topic, even more so given the increased use of global resources brought about by the pandemic. Although research on the addiction issue is available, there is still no up-to-date information on the level of mobility in Internet access, which is signaled by the growing popularity of smartphones. It is only possible to hypothesise that the level of mobility in accessing Internet resources is increasing. Despite the fact that the use of global sources in the educational process is stated, there is still an information deficit in examining the level of credibility of the content young people access during the educational process and to what extent the digital content they access is credible to them. There is a lack of sufficient and up-to-date information among publications on the structure of time spent by young people browsing online resources. Moreover, there is a lack of data on comparative characteristics, especially with regard to the same age users but from different continents. Equally important are the issues of accessibility to the Internet, which continues to be a problem, and the issues of the direction of mobility in the use of network resources including in regions with different levels of urbanisation.

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The purpose of this work is to provide knowledge in the areas of scientific interest indicated, in an international cross-section. For the purpose of achieving the above intention, the authors decided to formulate several research questions, the answer to which will allow to collect relevant information and provide knowledge that fills the observed cognitive gaps.

RQ1. Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Poland and Montenegro, regarding Internet accessibility and usage?

RQ2. Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Montenegro and Poland regarding tools to Internet access (and accessed Internet contents)?

The work, consisting of theoretical and empirical parts, is divided according to the scheme: literature review, research methods and techniques, and research results. The concluding part is the section entitled conclusions, which includes the final conclusion of the research with the most important content, but also formulates what limitations apply to the considerations made and what suggestions can be made for further research in the presented topic.

2. Literature review

The accessibility of global resources, which was created thanks to the Internet, is currently perceived as the norm without any special insight into the past aspect of accessibility to these resources. The point is that while some time ago it was possible to consider differences in access to the global network in such contexts as areas with better or worse access to the network, the quality of accessibility to the global network or the level of mobility in accessing the global network, currently these topics are addressed less frequently due to a definite improvement in accessibility.

The issue of accessibility to digital resources seems to be a natural privilege of every inhabitant of the planet. It should be noted that the topic addressed and still popular is, however, the issue of digital divide (van Dijk, 2005). The digital divide is not necessarily exclusively a matter of physical access to global resources although, of course, this problem cannot be completely ruled out, but among the various characteristics of the digital divide one can distinguish, for example, the range of activities that can be carried out via the Internet the range of available content to which users have access the level of freedom of time spent accessing global resources the range of activities that are possible with the help of the Internet.

According to the updated formulation of the digital divide, it is difficult to relate it solely to the question of having or not having access to global resources in favor of the question of assessing to what extent digitization is present in the life of each person and citizen, and how that person and citizen is able to use this opportunity and how he or she finds himself or herself in the digital reality (Castells, 2001). For this reason, the digital divide is gaining new importance in the context of social use and enjoyment of the benefits of digitization (Stanley,

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2003; Jenkins et al., 2006). Three aggregated levels indicating the existence of a digital divide are also mentioned (Hesper, 2021): the first level is related to devices and connections, the second level to effective use and digital skills, and the third level to the outcomes or benefits of using information and communication technologies (ICTs) .

This social reference to the digital divide seems to be indisputable and, as it were, highlights social differences into, among others, those with better or worse Internet literacy which, according to some researchers, is the basis of specific social status. Among the factors that affect the level of familiarity with the techniques of using Internet resources are age or the level and type of education, among others, which determine the level of ability to use the Internet in everyday life (van Dijk, 2005). However, these factors should not be considered as determining the ability to use the Internet (Mossberger et al., 2003).

Among the areas within which digital literacy can be identified and assessed is education (Shen & Jiang, 2002). Students, especially during the pandemic period, were virtually doomed to rely solely on electronic methods to acquire and develop knowledge. Moreover, the pandemic period itself was a time in which digital health literacy issues were a major theme (van der Vaart & Drossaert, 2017; Norman & Skinner, 2006). In addition to the process of knowledge transfer itself, which was referred to as i-learning or online teaching and learning, examination and testing of knowledge was also done through remote methods.

It seems that the age context in considering internet literacy is important if only for the level of intuitiveness, so to speak. The generation of young people, by virtue of the ubiquity of exposure to a wide range of electronic devices and thus access to the Internet, do not have much trouble with the novelties of digitization.

It seems that young generations also referred to as, among others, the z-generation or the millenials generation, but also others, are a specific group whose behavior relating to access to global resources seems to be important due to the Shaping the Future which is changing very dynamically is especially due to technological progress. The digital divide is related to age while the issue of territorial and cultural diversity that comes with it is the subject of research. There is a dramatic rise in digital media among lower and middle income nations (Cardon et al., 2009). According to the observed phenomena of the digital divide which is visible in the 65 plus group (Lapa et al., 2023) An important question is whether there are other types of factors besides age as to which disparity in the use and enjoyment of Internet resources is also noticeable. Concerning the results of surveys on Internet use and the level of professional si noticeable differences in European societies and the differences can be seen in Northern Europe versus Southern Europe and Eastern Europe versus Western Europe (van Dijk, 2009). Therefore, the issue of the level of wealth of societies as a factor in the level of

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skill in using the resources of the global network seems obvious while cultural issues are also pointed out as having an impact on digital literacy (Zhao et al., 2014).

Issues of diversity in digital literacy and technology may have cultural relevance due to the fact of different regulations that exist in different countries moreover, issues of class division may also affect access and use of various digital devices as well as policies and interpersonal relations. Among the factors that can culturally translate are also social factors such as exclusion at work. At the same time, social status and position can condition opportunities to deepen skills and access devices and resources, which can further foster the digital divide (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2019).

Among the factors with cultural characteristics that can affect the level of skills in using and exploiting global resources can also be mentioned cultural acceptance of digital tools and methods. Factors that also determine with them nice inclinations to use and enjoy digital resources are differences in the context of individualism/collectivism, or masculinity/femininity (Tarhini et al., 2017).

In addition to the issue of accessibility to global resources which seem to be of invaluable importance in the development of the economy and social relations, the dangers that come with this access play an important role. Of the dangers associated with access to the Internet, the main one is the so-called addictive browsing of the Internet. The global prevalence of internet addiction, estimated to affect around 210 million individuals, underscores the widespread impact of this issue. Despite its prevalence, there is no universally accepted definition of internet addiction. Instead, it is often characterized by its effects. Individuals spending more than 40 hours per week online could be considered addicted, but this metric has been criticized for oversimplification. In today's digital age, professionals often spend substantial time on the internet due to work demands, complicating the classification as prolonged internet use doesn't necessarily equate to addiction.

Kardefelt-Winther (2014) distinguishes between "high involvement" and "dysfunctional involvement" in internet use. High involvement refers to significant internet use that remains functional, such as for work or academic purposes, while dysfunctional involvement describes internet use that interferes with an individual's daily life and overall well-being. Understanding this distinction is crucial in determining whether an individual's internet use is problematic. Research has shown that moderate internet use, especially for academic or social purposes, can have positive effects on mental well-being and social relationships, particularly among adolescents and younger users.

3. Research methodology

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The selection of the literature used for the analysis was made through keywords related to the definitions of Internet usage, but also the areas of internet usage and also the question of overestimated time for internet usage. In addition to the literature analysis conducted, questions have been also formulated for the research questionnaire and this has been initiated during the secondments. The substrate for creating the issues to which the respondents were asked to respond was the material collected during the study visits of the co-authors of the text, from countries such as Poland, Montenegro and Indonesia. The study visits constituted a stage of the international project "Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia" ODDEA, Project No. 101086381 under Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1. Each of the co-authors of the present work participated as a seconded Staff on a minimum one-month research study visit. The regularities and behaviors of the students observed during the study visits provided the material, for the formulation of the research questions, as well as the questions for the questionnaire.

The main research objective of the paper is to provide knowledge in the areas of internet usage, specifically in different countries, also culturally diverse. For the purpose of achieving the above intention, the authors decided to formulate two general research questions, the answer to which will allow to collect relevant information and provide knowledge that fills the observed cognitive gaps. The research questions formulated are also the fundamental base for the literature review analysis as well as for the creation of the research questionnaire. There have been formulated the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1. Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Poland and Montenegro, regarding Internet accessibility and usage?

RQ2. Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Montenegro and Poland regarding tools to Internet access (and accessed Internet contents)?

The target population were the youth population in Poland, Montenegro and Indonesia among whom a questionnaire was distributed without translation to native language. It had been titled "The social impact of internet-based content for young people," and was posted on the Google Forms platform in October 2023. The survey was available to students for the next six months. Students studying in Poland, Montenegro and Indonesia were asked to complete the questionnaire, while those participating in the survey represented different countries and nationalities. All project objectives leading to the preparation and realization of the research idea have been presented to the parties taking part in the survey. The representatives taking part in the survey were not just students from cited countries, but also those representing the surrounding regions, thus Indonesian and surrounding countries students were answering the questions, also more than just Montenegrin students took part in the survey (Serbian, Bosnian and Herzegovinian, but also other, all those from the South Balkan countries. The same situation referred to Poland where students from Germany, Ukraine, but also Slovakia just to mention few of them, had taken part in the survey. Although this different nationalities were

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engaged in the research results obtaining, the authors of this work had decided to title the representation of the respondents by the national perspective of where the study had taken part. This to even higher extent results from the majority of the Polish, Montenegrin and Indonesian nationalities.

Apart from the core questions there were metric questions about age, gender, employment, education, nationality, country, but also about place of residence (where most of the time is spent), to enable analysis of the relationship between students from less vs. more urban areas and to determine transformative potential. At the same time, however, also taking into account such information would have made it possible to gain general knowledge about the level of saturation of access to global resources. Also, it would be possible to do more analyses and make a wider range of correlations.

4. Results

In total there were collected 332 responses, among which 130(39,16%) from Indonesia, 109(32,83%) from Montenegro and 93(28,01%) from Poland. Table I shows the essential characteristics of the sample. There is a gender misbalance among sample in Indonesia and Montenegro, with majority of male population. Also, the majority of the samples in each country is of age 19-21 which is fully in line with the study objectives.

TABLE I. Sample characteristics (n=332)

Concept/ Variable	Indonesia	Montenegro	Poland
Gender			
Female	27 (20.77%)	35 (31.11%)	47 (50.54%)
Male	103 (79.23%)	74 (67.89%)	46 (49.46%)
Age			
16-18	4 (3.08%)	12 (11.01%)	3 (3.23%)
19-21	117 (90.00%)	87 (79.82%)	78 (83.87%)
22-25	9 (6.92%)	8 (7.34%)	11 (11.83%)
31-40	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.83%)	1 (1.08%)
Level of Education			
Bachelor (BA or BSc)	38 (29.23%)	23 (21.10%)	13 (13.98%)
Primary school graduate	11 (8.46%)	7 (6.42%)	0 (0.00%)
Secondary School Graduate	81 (62.31%)	77 (70.64%)	79 (84.95%)
Master (MA or MSc) graduate	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.83%)	1 (1.08%)

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Table II shows employment status and residence location of the sample. Young persons participating in the study are mainly unemployed, while at least a half of responders within each country live in big towns or cities, e.g. 49,23% from Indonesia, 61.47% from Montenegro and 81.72% from Poland.

TABLE II. Employment status and residence location (n=332)

Concept/ Variable	Indonesia	Montenegro	Poland
Employment Status			
Unemployed	99 (76.15%)	74 (67.89%)	62 (66.67%)
Full-time employed	1 (0.77%)	11 (10.09%)	1 (1.08%)
Internship	2 (1.54%)	2 (1.83%)	1 (1.08%)
Part-Time employed	18 (13.85%)	15 (13.76%)	23 (24.73%)
Self-Employed	10 (7.69%)	7 (6.42%)	6 (6.45%)
Residence			
Countryside (up to 200)	13 (10.00%)	10 (9.17%)	2 (2.15%)
Countryside (200-1000)	16 (12.31%)	6 (5.50%)	6 (6.45%)
Community rural-urban (1-5k)	8 (6.15%)	6 (5.50%)	4 (4.30%)
Community urban (<5k)	4 (3.08%)	8 (7.34%)	1 (1.08%)
Little town (5-10k)	25 (19.23%)	12 (11.01%)	4 (4.30%)
Big Town (10-500k)	31 (23.85%)	54 (49.54%)	11 (11.83%)
City (500k+)	33 (25.38%)	13 (11.93%)	65 (69.89%)

Results on research questions

RQ1. Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Poland and Montenegro, regarding Internet accessibility and usage?

First of all, the characteristics of access to the global network among the study participants, i.e. representatives of three culturally diverse regions, were compared: Indonesia, Montenegro, Poland. The analysis of cross-country differences regarding students' Internet access and its usage is conducted by analyzing the access to high-speed Internet in both urban and rural areas (Figure 1)

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Figure 1. High-speed Internet access vs. level of urbanization in respective countries

The results of the survey clearly illustrate that in each of the analyzed regions, students in the vast majority (around 60%) use high-speed access to the global network, moreover, this applies to both urbanized and non-urbanized areas. As noted earlier, the issue of greater propensity for addiction was confronted in the study with ease of access to the Internet. What emerges from the results of the survey is that among the analyzed groups of young people there is a perception of a similar level, a high level of accessibility to the global network, which has a direct reflection on the answer to research question No. 1. From the information that results from the study findings, there is no significant difference in access to the Internet between the analyzed countries.

Figure 1 provides also the comparative data on the relationship in high-speed Internet access to the level of urbanization in the three geographic and cultural areas being compared. Furthermore it also provides information on the variation in high-speed Internet access (fiber and 5G, 4G) vs. slower Internet access, which allows us to determine the level of access and the level of modernity of this access.

In the surveyed countries, the level of high-speed Internet access can be considered high, the weakest overall result (urban and rural areas) of Internet access is recorded by Poland, however, the deviation is not so large in relation to the compared regions. In the context of the overall survey, the question of the level of easy and fast access to the Internet is crucial. This

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is because it means quick and easy access to Internet resources with pro-creative characteristics - valuable from the point of view of being able to redirect the interests of people who spend a lot of time in front of a screen.

RQ2: Is there a cross-country divide between Indonesia, Montenegro and Poland regarding tools to Internet access and accessed Internet contents?

The next stage of research was connected with the second research question about the potential divide between different geographically located users in terms of tools used to access. In order to obtain the initial information on the specificity of IT equipment used for global network accessing the question were prepared and distributed as being one of the research questionnaire sections.

In order to respond to the RQ2 two dimensional analysis have been made: primarily (i) differences in methods and devices for Internet access, and secondly (ii) differences in preferences for selection of the content type and sources. Table III presents results of the statistically processed information about what are more and less preferred means of internet access among students from three studied regions. The information sought referred to the state of contents, which would then be compared to the potential status of possible addictive behaviors. As previously stated, what has been evidenced is the dependency between global resources contents accessibility easiness vs propensity to be affected with the internet addiction. The positive relationship between the two variables can thus be utilized for the current study purposes. While the high speed internet access is similar and at the very high level, with no specific differences between the studied regions, then further analysis can lead to the point where this accessibility can no necessarily be the reason for addictive internet usage attitudes if observed. The data illustrated at Table III allows for searching for differences as well as models of internet usage in studied countries.

TABLE III. Usage of different devices for Internet access

Concept/ Variable	Indonesia	Montenegro	Poland
Smartphone			
Primary or secondary most important tool	128 (98,46%)	100 (91,74%)	90 (97,78%)
Rarely or Not used	1 (0,77%)	4 (3,67%)	1 (1,07%)
Tablet			
Primary or secondary most important tool	18 (13,85%)	20 (18,35%)	21 (22,83%)
Rarely or Not used	92 (70,77%)	63 (57,79%)	59 (64,13%)
LaptopPC			
Primary or secondary most important tool	111 (85,38%)	66 (60,55%)	52 (55,91%)
Rarely or Not used	8 (6,15%)	20 (18,35%)	24 (25,81%)
Laptop MAC			

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Primary or secondary most important tool	24 (18,46%)	28 (25,69%)	19 (20,43%)
Rarely or Not used	102 (78,46%)	61 (55,96%)	65 (69,89%)
Personal computer			
Primary or secondary most important tool	35 (26,92%)	61 (55,96%)	26 (27,96%)
Rarely or Not used	81 (62,31%)	23 (21,69%)	51 (54,84%)
Personal computer MAC			
Primary or secondary most important tool	7 (5,38%)	17 (15,59%)	11 (11,83%)
Rarely or Not used	117 (90,00%)	69 (63,30%)	74 (79,57%)
Smartwatch			
Primary or secondary most important tool	12 (9,23%)	21 (19,27%)	13 (13,98%)
Rarely or Not used	102 (78,46%)	63 (57,79%)	66 (71,74%)
TV			
Primary or secondary most important tool	17 (13,08%)	31 (28,44%)	15 (16,30%)
Rarely or Not used	71 (54,62%)	35 (32,11%)	45 (48,91%)

Table III shows that smartphones are mainly used for accessing the Internet in all countries, while smartwatches, even being highly popular among young population are not used for this purpose. Usage of other devices slightly differs between countries. Another thing relates to how the issue of accessibility to global digital resources regardless of their type currently stands and also how this access looks in the context of mobility, i.e., the more mobile the access to the Internet, the easier it is to access digital sources and thus, the less chance of addictive use of the Internet, according to research conducted earlier (cited in Lit. Review).

The results of the survey indicate that the markets of young people in the countries analyzed are virtually fully saturated with cell phones - this is the primary source of access to the global network, irrespective of country or region. The popularity of the tablet is behind that of the laptop computer. Similarly, the popularity of the desktop computer, while greater than that of tablet use, is receding from that of the laptop. The smartphone and laptop are the tools used most often to access online content. The quality of access is therefore accompanied by the convenience of mobility guaranteed by laptops, and even more so by smartphones. This is reflected in each of the regions studied. The lack of significant differences in the instruments that enable access to the global network applies to all the regions analyzed, this one also to the issue of the level of urbanization within the countries analyzed.

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To complement the information on Internet behavior, we analyzed what content is primarily of interest to users in the three distinguished regions. Therefore, students’ habits are analyzed based on questions within variable Main tools for Internet usage, as presented in the table. An ANOVA test performed on the dataset indicated differences in the responses of students from various countries. Specifically, the responses varied regarding the percentage of time spent on different types of online content—relaxation, research or educational purposes, and traditional sources for homework preparation—among students from Indonesia, Montenegro, and Poland, as presented in Table IV.

In order to identify the exact differences, Post Hoc test was conducted. Pairs of countries differing in answers were Poland-Montenegro and Indonesia-Poland, within questions 2.1-2.4. No differences were identified within Q5. Most of the respondents (37.63%) from Poland estimated their time spent on social media (Q2.2) within 0-20%, whereas respondents from Indonesia and Montenegro estimated 25,38% and 29.92%, respectfully. The most common answer to Q2.3 within Polish respondents was 20-40%, while in Indonesia and Montenegro it was ranked #3 (having 20.8% and 22.0% respectfully). Traditional sources of information were significantly less important in Poland when compared to Indonesia and Montenegro (54.8% in Poland – 37.7% in Indonesia and 27.5% in Montenegro).

TABLE IV

Analysis of difference between regions regarding *preferable content used from the Internet* (ANOVA results)

No.	Question	ANOVA results
Q2.1	Social media	F (331,2) = 1.193, p<0.05
Q2.2	Relaxing content	F (330,2) = 7.325, p<0.000
Q2.3	Research/educational contents	F (331,2) = 7.141, p<0.000
Q2.4	Traditional sources of information for preparing homework and projects	F (330,2) = 10.117, p<0.000
Q2.5	Digital sources of information for preparing homework and projects	F (330,2) = 0.690, p<0.5

Hence, as the analysis shows, just as there were no significant differences in access to the global network, there were no differences in terms of the global resources and content that students from the analyzed countries reach for, which negatively answers the second research question posed.

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6. Conclusions

Digitalization driving globalization processes, as well as globalization moderating digitalization processes, are factors resulting in an increase in time spent in front of a computer monitor. In addition to the noticeable positive effects, which are undoubtedly related to the supportive function of computer systems, the negative effects of too long, uncontrolled and addictive interaction with the computer have also been recognized. The problematic nature arises both from too long a period of time devoted to the computer and, in particular, using it to browse Internet resources, but also because of the negative effects that this browsing causes mainly in young people.

The literature recognizes the positive links of the intuitive pro-technology behavior of young generations, which even in this vein are defined as babyboomers, or Generation Z, among others, but less noticeably opines on the dark side of the addictive impact on young people of being able to access Internet resources effortlessly, at any time of the day or night.

This abuse of the computer, which mainly affects the younger generations, although not exclusively, has its negative consequences, among which the impact on physical and mental health has been recognized. After all, too little physical activity results in an unnatural mode of physical development, and consequently can also strike at the mental health and well-being of young people.

The purpose of the study was to gain knowledge about the type of time spent in front of the computer by first and second degree students from different European countries and for comparison with students from Indonesia (also first and second degree). The selection of countries was not only facilitated because of the jointly conducted ODDEA project within Horizon Europe. The results of the literature analysis indicated that there may be differences in internet use between European and Asian students as this is related to the cultural issues, however at the level of countries the age factor seems to be the same problem in every nation. Generational differences matter in terms of digital divide. In order to be able to make a more complete comparative analysis and especially students who were the study target group, the study included not only the behavioral directions of students in the context of using Internet resources. Among the questions to respondents (students) were also asked about what area they live in terms of urbanization and the situation itself with access to Internet resources. The context of ease of access to global digital resources was also surveyed.

As a result of the analyses of the students' responses, the following conclusions emerged, answering the research questions formulated earlier:

- There is no noticeable difference between the analyzed countries in either internet accessibility or usage. In each of the culturally and geographically diverse areas analyzed, respondents indicated a high level of broadband accessibility. The level of accessibility in rural areas is at a similar fairly high level in the analyzed countries. Thus, in each of the analyzed countries, accessibility to a variety of content is relatively easy, with no problems. It is worth noting, however, that between 20% and

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30% of responses about poor or no broadband coverage means that there is still a need for quality access to the world's online resources.

- Similar to the situation of the level of accessibility to the Internet is that relating to the devices by which this access is obtained. In each of the countries studied, among the group of young people interested in improving their education, we can observe interest mainly in mobile Internet access, as the main two devices via which this access occurs are the smartphone and laptop. The tablet is not the main tool, but of moderate popularity. In addition to the fact that smartphones actually reign supreme as devices that are the gateway to global content, they are held by virtually all Internet users, regardless of region. Comparable to the homogeneity of responses in terms of the devices used that give access to the network is the situation with the content itself. The structure of the analyzed resources is similar in the analyzed countries (relaxation content, social media, educational and research content).
- There is no noticeable difference between the analyzed countries in either internet accessibility or usage. In each of the culturally and geographically diverse areas analyzed, respondents indicated a high level of broadband accessibility. The level of accessibility in rural areas is at a similar fairly high level in the analyzed countries. Thus, in each of the analyzed countries, accessibility to a variety of content is relatively easy, with no problems. It is worth noting, however, that between 20% and 30% of responses about poor or no broadband coverage means that there is still a need for quality access to the world's online resources.

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